

101112153 -CLAIMS

An innovative decision-support system for improved care pathways for patients with neurodegenerative diseases and comorbidities

WP5 – Digital health tools – Companion app

D5.1 - Integration of test battery for cognition and fine motor skills into icompanion app

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the CLAIMS Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

Acronym	Participant organisation name
CHARITE	Charité - Universitaetsmedizin Berlin (Coordinator)
SYNAPSE	Synapse Research Management Partners SL
ICO	Icometrix NV (Project Leader)
RUB	Ruhr-Universitaet Bochum
TUD	Technische Universitaet Dresden
CHUL	Université de Lille
CCI	Casa Di Cura Igea
GUHP	Vseobecna Fakultni Nemocnice v Praze
ECF	European Charcot Foundation
AALTO	Aalto University
ROCHE	F. Hoffmann- La Roche AG
BMS	Bristol-Myers Squibb
IMCYSE	Imcyse SA
ABS	AB Science SA
NOC	Nocturne

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the CLAIMS project (101112153).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The CLAIMS Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst CLAIMS participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Cognitive impairment is a significant burden for people with Multiple Sclerosis (pwMS), affecting their employment, mental health, and social activities. It is estimated that up to 70% of the estimated 2.8 million pwMS worldwide experience cognitive impairment. This impacts the patient's information processing speed, working memory, attention, and visuospatial abilities. Traditional neuropsychological tests to assess this, such as the Symbol Digit Modalities Test (SDMT) and Nine-Hole Peg Test (9HPT), often face challenges like practice effects, improper administration, and the stress of clinical visits. All of these could result in skewed test results. As such, there is a need for reliable, accessible tools for assessing cognitive function and manual dexterity in pwMS.

The CLAIMS project has contributed to the development and validation of two smartphone-based tests for integration into the icompanion app: the icompanion Symbol Test and the icompanion Finger Dexterity Test. These digital tests are designed to be used remotely by pwMS, providing them the option for continuous self-monitoring between hospital visits. The icompanion Symbol Test is based on the SDMT and measures information processing speed by counting correct symbol matches within a 90-second interval. The icompanion Finger Dexterity Test mimics the 9HPT and assesses manual dexterity by timing the sequence of steps required to "fry and serve" virtual eggs on a smartphone screen.

Both tests were rigorously validated. The icompanion Symbol Test showed strong correlations with the paper-pencil SDMT ($r=.63$, $p<.001$) and significant relationships with MS-related biomarkers linked to disease progression such as thalamic volume and juxtacortical lesions. The icompanion Finger Dexterity Test demonstrated significant correlations with the 9HPT and was sensitive to differences between pwMS and healthy controls.

A real-world validation study (CogMS) revealed a less strong correlation between subjective (based on patient reported outcomes) and objective (based on the icompanion Symbol Test) cognitive assessments, indicating that self-reports may not always reliably predict cognitive impairment. Objective cognitive performance was more closely linked to physical measures such as walking ability, while subjective cognition correlated with internal experiences like pain, fatigue, and depression. This highlights the importance of objective cognitive monitoring to avoid biases inherent to self-assessments.

Patient feedback on the 2 digital tests was overwhelmingly positive, with a strong preference for digital assessments over traditional paper-based methods. Both digital tests received excellent usability scores, supporting their potential for widespread clinical adoption.

The Symbol Test and Finger Dexterity Test will be available in the upcoming version 3.0.0 of the icompanion app. These tests offer a practical, reliable means for continuous remote self-monitoring of cognitive and finger dexterity impairments in pwMS. By providing objective assessments that correlate with important neurological biomarkers, these tools have the potential to significantly enhance patient care and disease progression monitoring.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Cognitive impairment

Cognitive impairment poses a substantial burden for people with Multiple Sclerosis (pwMS), impacting their employment, mental health, and social activities. Research indicates that up to 70% of the estimated 2.8 million pwMS worldwide experience cognitive impairment. This impairment notably affects information processing speed and working memory, as well as attention and visuospatial abilities, even in those with mild physical symptoms. However, accurately assessing cognitive function in clinical practice is challenging for several reasons. Patients taking neuropsychological tests to assess cognition, like the Symbol Digit Modalities Test (SDMT), often exhibit strong learning or practice effects, leading to inconsistent results. Additionally, inadequate training of the staff administering these tests and improper test administration further complicate assessment. Moreover, performing these tests during a visit can be stressful for patients, particularly those with physical disabilities, and may not reflect their true cognitive abilities. And lastly, conducting tests during relapses, when cognitive function may be temporarily affected, will also bias results.

1.2 Finger dexterity impairment

Approximately 60-75% of pwMS having mild disability also show signs of impaired manual dexterity, with prevalence increasing as the disease worsens. This impairment is related to decreased strength, sensory dysfunction and/or tremor and ultimately, this results in decreased participation in social, home, and productive activities. The nine-hole peg test (9HPT) is considered the golden standard for the assessment of manual dexterity in MS. In this test, patients have to place nine pegs into nine holes and subsequently remove them one by one. This test has a good convergent, discriminant and ecological validity and test-retest reliability. However, its administration requires clinic visits, appropriate material and trained personnel, which not all clinical sites have the resources for. Furthermore, there are significant practice effects after repeated administration, resulting in a biased estimation of finger dexterity. Additionally, MS is characterized by important fluctuations of symptoms due to temperature changes and fatigue. The moment of a clinical visit, which in itself can be a cause for stress and fatigue, might thus not be the most accurate representation of an individual's function over longer periods of time.

1.3 Digital cognition and finger dexterity tests

Patient care is increasingly digitalizing as these digital tools often provide very practical solutions for the challenges faced by pwMS and therefore are well-accepted by these patients. Additionally, their feasibility and cost-effectiveness have also been established previously and contribute to their acceptance. Patients moreover tend to objectively benefit from these approaches, for example for fatigue management and improving cognitive function. The latter is important as nearly half of the people with MS have cognitive impairment, which is associated with significant financial burden, productivity, and decreased mental well-being. It is hypothesized that cognitive problems in MS start with slower information processing speed. To address the need for digital tests to better monitor pwMS, we have developed and validated two tests with the goal of integrating them into icompanion: A digital version of the SDMT and 9HPT will serve as a remote screening tools which patients can perform in between hospital visits to monitor their cognition and hand function.

1.3.1 icompanion Symbol Test

The icompanion Symbol Test is based on its paper variant called the SDMT, which is considered the gold standard for cognitive screening in MS. This test captures information processing speed of the patient by counting the number of correct symbols within a 90-second interval. This digital variant that will be added to the icompanion app is a combination of symbols which are presented on the phone screen of the subject, one at a time. Furthermore, a key is presented on top, which consists of 9 pairs of symbols, and which shuffles every trial. For every trial, the subject needs to indicate whether the combination occurs in the key on top. A practice phase precedes the actual testing phase. The total score is the number of correct answers in 90 seconds, in line with the paper variant.

1.3.2 icompanion Finger Dexterity Test

The icompanion Finger Dexterity test is based on its in-clinic variant called the 9HPT, which is considered the golden standard for the assessment of manual dexterity in MS. This test measures the time that is needed for the subject to move 9 'pegs' out of and back into a board equipped with corresponding holes. For this digital variant that will be added to the icompanion app, the goal is similar as the patient has to fry and subsequently serve a total of 10 eggs as quickly as possible. For each of the 10 eggs, a sequence of steps is performed. First, an egg is presented on the screen, which the subject has to break by pinching it between two fingers. In a second step, the subject needs to drag the egg to a frying pan, where it is cooked after releasing the egg. Finally, the cooked egg is pinched once again and dragged to a plate, where it is served. This combination of movements mimics the movements involved in the 9HPT. A practice phase of 10 eggs precedes the actual testing phase. The entire test is performed first with the dominant hand and subsequently with the non-dominant hand.

2 VALIDATION OF BOTH TESTS

The tests were both developed, clinically validated, and evaluated for usability by icometrix. The outcomes of these validations and evaluations are described in full in the following papers:

- Van Laethem, D., Denissen, S., Costers, L., Descamps, A., Baijot, J., Van Remoortel, A., ... & Nagels, G. (2024). The Finger Dexterity Test: validation study of a smartphone-based manual dexterity assessment. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, 30(1), 121-130.
- Denissen, S., Van Laethem, D., Baijot, J., Costers, L., Descamps, A., Van Remoortel, A., ... & Nagels, G. (2023). icognition: a smartphone-based cognitive screening battery. *medRxiv*, 2023-07.
- The peer-reviewed publication on the real-world multi-center international validation and usability testing of icognition is currently being prepared.

2.1 Concurrent validation

The icompanion Symbol Test showed a strong correlation with its paper-pencil equivalent ($r=.63$, $p<.001$) as tested in 101 pwMS. The icompanion Finger Dexterity test was significantly correlated with the Nine-Hole Peg Test (dominant hand: $r = 0.62$, $p = 2.64e-08$; non-dominant: $r = 0.51$, $p = 2.69e-05$) as tested in 65 pwMS.

2.2 Clinical validation

The icompanion Symbol Test showed a negative correlation with the Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) ($r=-.27$, $p=.01$) as tested in 101 pwMS, and a strong correlation with thalamic volume ($\rho = 0.49$, $p = 0.001$) and juxtacortical lesions ($\rho = -0.36$, $p = 0.022$), important signs of MS-related neurological damage, as tested in 52 pwMS.

The icompanion Finger Dexterity test showed a significant difference between the pwMS and healthy controls (dominant: $p = 4.51e-09$; non-dominant: $p = 3.38e-09$) and a significant correlation with the EDSS (dominant: $r = 0.37$, $p = 0.004$; non-dominant: $r = 0.34$, $p = 0.012$) as tested in 65 pwMS.

2.3 Test-retest reliability

The icompanion Symbol Test shows high test-retest reliability ($r=.81$, $p<.001$) in 101 pwMS. The icompanion Finger Dexterity tests showed high test-retest reliability for the dominant and non-dominant hand ($\rho = 0.71$, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.82$, $p < 0.001$) in 65 pwMS.

2.4 Real world-validation

CogMS is an observational, cross-sectional, remote, real-world study of cognitive function in pwMS. We investigated the correlation between subjective and objective patient self-evaluations of cognitive function while also investigating the prevalence of objective cognitive impairment in different EDSS strata of pwMS.

pwMS were stratified by EDSS to evaluate the correlation between objective and subjective cognition in three different EDSS strata (EDSS 0 - 2; 2.5 - 3.5; 4.0 - 5.5) and the occurrence of objective cognitive dysfunction in these EDSS stages of MS. All data was captured using the icompanion app in a remote, non-clinical setting (i.e., patient's home) within three weeks of patient onboarding. In the icompanion app, patients were asked to perform the icompanion Symbol Test (objective testing) together with patient-reported outcomes (PROs) for subjective cognition, MS symptoms, pEDSS, depression and fatigue. If available, a recent (max. 6 months) MRI scan was provided from which volumetric measurements can be calculated using icometrix' icobrain ms software. Finally, patients were asked to answer questions on their experiences with cognition since diagnosis, their preferences and opinions about cognition as a treatment goal, the usability of the icognition battery, and the preference compared to paper-based neuropsychological tests.

In the study we found a significant but weak correlation between subjective and objective cognitive assessments among pwMS, indicating that subjective measures may not reliably predict objective cognitive impairment. This is consistent with previous research suggesting MS patients may not accurately recognize their cognitive status. Our data revealed that subjective and objective impairments seldom co-occur, which challenges the assumption that subjective reports can act as proxies for objective cognitive decline.

When investigating the relationship of subjective or objective cognition with potential covariates such as (self-reported) MS symptoms, body function, fatigue and depression, it became clear that subjective cognition was strongly related to most of the self-reported variables, and especially pain, fatigue and depression. On the other hand, objective cognitive performance could only be linked to self-reported walking ability. The divergence in the factors that correlate with subjective and objective measures points to the existence of two separate cognitive entities, with subjective cognition being linked to more subjective, invisible and internal experiences and objective cognition being linked to more physical or objective measures such as walking ability. This highlights the importance of monitoring cognitive impairment in an objective way, as this is less biased by subjective and more invisible symptoms than subjective estimations of patients' own cognition.

This was further confirmed by the relationship between objective cognitive performance and brain volumetric biomarkers. We observed a strong relationship with thalamus volume, which is heavily involved in the cognitive processes underlying the icompanion Symbol test, as well as relationships with juxtacortical lesions, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), occipital lobe cortical grey matter volume and hippocampus volume. These findings highlight the clinical relevance of the objective cognitive assessment that is the icompanion Symbol test, showing its ability to detect cognitive changes that align with both widespread and localized neurodegenerative changes in MS. Consequently, this test could serve as an effective instrument for tracking cognitive decline and the progression of MS, complementing traditional structural neuroimaging biomarkers.

Besides providing evidence for the relevance of objectively monitoring cognition and the clinical relevance of the icompanion Symbol test, it is crucial for the (continued) clinical use of digital objective cognitive assessments that the tool is well-received by patients. Subjects in the study scored icompanion an excellent usability score (System Usability Score questionnaire), and significantly preferred the icompanion digital assessments over traditional paper-based methods such as the SDMT, underscoring its potential for broader adoption in clinical practice.

In conclusion, this study provided evidence for the clinical relevance of the icompanion Symbol test by showing a disconnect from subjective cognition and a relationship with important imaging biomarkers. The study also demonstrated strong acceptance of the test by patients, encouraging the clinical adoption of the tool.

3 INTEGRATION OF TEST BATTERY

3.1 Design and development

The implementation of the icompanion Symbol Test and Finger Dexterity Test is currently ongoing. Some delays occurred due to the regulatory approval from icometrix' notified body in Europe, which had a backlog of multiple months before responding to icometrix and will now require an assessment of the technical documentation before icognition can be released in Europe. We would like to note that the final implementation might still slightly differ from the images below. As the development of the icompanion medical device software follows the requirements of IEC 62304:2006/A1:2015, an extensive risk analysis was performed before implementation.

3.2 Smartphone app

In terms of technical implementation, some mock-ups of the implementation in the icompanion smartphone app can be found below (note: Cognition and Dexterity refer to the Symbol Test and Finger Dexterity Test). Patients will be able to set goals for which domains they might want to track, since not for all patients it would make sense to track each domain. Patients are recommended to make this selection together with their care provider. Since the icompanion app is built around working from visit to visit, the tests will now be part of the visit preparation module. Before performing the tests, we provide a small introduction to the tests, and we instruct patients to e.g. be in a distraction-free environment.

3.3 HCP platform

In parallel, integration of the test results into the icompanion Healthcare Provider (HCP) portal is ongoing. Multiple mock-ups of the new portal and integrated tests were presented to clinicians such as Dr. Guy Nagels (UZ Brussel), Dr. Tjalf Ziemssen (Dresden, DE), Dr. Barbara Willekens & Judith Derdelinckx (UZA, BE), Dr. Maarten Dewil (Imelda Ziekenhuis, BE), Dr. Enrique Alvarez (UCHealth, USA), Dr. Dana Horakova (Prague, CZ), Dr. Klaus Schmierer (Queen Mary, UK). All clinicians found the addition of the test values relevant and interesting with "clear added value" (cf. Barbara Willekens).

The values will be presented in the patient dashboard (displayed below, see values in the red rectangle) and in a more detailed data overview with more longitudinal graphs (combined with other PRO, passive monitoring and treatment data).

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the CLAIMS project has successfully supported the development and validation of two innovative smartphone-based objective assessments, one for cognition and one to assess finger dexterity.

The digital icompanion Symbol Test and Finger Dexterity Test offer practical, remote screening tools that patients can use between hospital visits to monitor their cognitive and hand functions. These tools are designed to overcome the limitations of traditional neuropsychological tests, such as practice effects, improper administration, and the stress associated with clinical visits. By providing objective and consistent measurements, these tests can help in better understanding and tracking the progression of MS-related impairments.

The validation studies demonstrated strong correlations with established clinical tests and significant relationships with important MS-related biomarkers, affirming the clinical relevance of these digital assessments. Additionally, the high test-retest reliability further validates the robustness of these tools.

The real-world validation study highlighted a weak correlation between subjective and objective cognitive assessments, underscoring the need for this objective monitoring through the digital Symbol Test. The significant associations between objective cognitive performance and brain volumetric biomarkers also emphasize the potential of the icompanion Symbol Test in detecting and tracking cognitive changes in MS.

Moreover, the positive feedback from patients regarding the usability and preference for the icompanion digital assessments over traditional methods supports the broader adoption of these tools in clinical practice. The integration of these tests into the icompanion platform, accessible via smartphones, aligns with the increasing trend towards digital healthcare solutions, offering a convenient and effective means for ongoing patient monitoring.

As the development of the icompanion medical device software continues, the upcoming version 3.0.0 will finalize the implementation of these assessments, enhancing the platform's capabilities. The successful rollout of these tests will provide healthcare professionals with valuable tools for more accurate and timely assessments of cognitive and finger dexterity impairments in pwMS, ultimately improving patient care and outcomes.